

Impact of familial support on a high school female student's academic performance in STEM disciplines in Lahore, Pakistan

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1. Abstract

This study investigates how familial support influences female students' participation and performance in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education in Pakistan. Using a mixed-methods approach, surveys and interviews were conducted with high school girls in Lahore. The findings reveal that while patriarchal norms persist, many families, especially in urban middle-class households, are increasingly supportive of their daughters' STEM ambitions. Emotional encouragement emerged as a more critical factor than financial resources. However, societal pressures, traditional career expectations, and lack of female role models continue to pose significant challenges. The research highlights the evolving role of family dynamics in shaping girls' access to STEM fields in Pakistan.

Keywords: Female STEM Participation, Pakistan Education, Familial Influence, Societal Barriers

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2. Introduction

Despite widespread conversations about gender equality in recent decades, female representation in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) fields remains strikingly low across the globe. In 2023, women made up only 28% of the STEM workforce, with regional disparities even more pronounced: it stands at 24% in the United States, 17% in the European Union, 16% in Japan, and 14% in India (MIT, Gender Gap in STEM, 2023). In Pakistan, the figures are even more discouraging. Women overall make up only 24% of the labour force (Labour Force Survey 2018-19), and only 1% of women in Pakistan work in technology, as per a report conducted by the local advocacy group Circle Women.

This utter lack of female representation in STEM fields in Pakistan points to various causes that need to be addressed, including familial support. Conservative societies like Pakistan, where women are told to conform to certain stereotypes, make it increasingly difficult for young girls to step out of their comfort zone and pursue their passions besides the careers dictated to them by their family figures. Many young girls are encouraged to pursue careers deemed "appropriate" for women, such as teaching or healthcare, while fields like engineering, computing, or physics are dismissed as unfit or too challenging. Lack of support can be a critical factor determining how far a young girl can progress against a society drenched in gender bias and fearful of social stigma. On the other hand, a nurturing environment can help her to pursue male-dominated careers like STEM, thus dictating her academic performance.

This paper seeks to examine the extent to which familial support impacts a high school female student's academic performance in STEM disciplines in Pakistan. By investigating the relationship between a student's home environment and her educational outcomes, this study aims to highlight the critical role families play in either enabling or limiting girls' academic success. The objectives of the study are threefold:

2.1. Objectives:

1. To explore the relationship between family dynamics and female academic achievement in STEM.
2. To present statistical evidence of gender disparities within Pakistani households and educational systems.
3. To demonstrate, through interviews and data, how a positive family environment can empower female students to succeed in challenging academic fields.

3. Literature Review

In Pakistan, girls make up 57% of out-of-school children and face systemic discrimination in education (Hollows, Rab & Schulze, 2021). While gender parity at the tertiary level is nearly achieved, complete parity remains elusive across all levels, especially in STEM careers. A British Council study found societal beliefs view STEM as unprofitable or unsuitable for women, except medicine, with a psychological barrier where all student focus groups doubted their ability, reinforced by 63% of staff. Social constraints like marriage and motherhood further limit STEM involvement, seen as a means to improve marriage prospects. Wealthier families support girls' access to STEM, but participation drops sharply after secondary school, with only 47% of girls versus 72% of boys enrolled in STEM classes. Nonetheless, 71% agree that gendered subject patterns should change, indicating a shift in attitudes. Limitations include regional cultural norms, lack of longitudinal data, and limited data from underrepresented regions like Balochistan.

Building on the theme of parental influence, Hasan et al. (2025) highlight patriarchal norms shaping educational outcomes, with many parents believing girls should stay home and support gender equality, varying by gender, through a regional survey of 350 families. Family structures often fail to support female education due to financial, domestic, and safety concerns. The study's regional focus limits broader applicability, and the data do not specify socioeconomic factors or policy impacts. Qaisar (2023) found that gender stereotypes and domestic burdens discourage women in rural areas from STEM, while urban areas show higher participation. Future research should examine both genders across disciplines with larger samples. Kiazai (2025) surveyed parent engagement in Quetta, finding most parents support students' education but with limited involvement in school activities, and lacked detailed analysis by gender or socioeconomic status.

In another research, Kalsoom, Jabeen, and Khalid et al (2020), found through a quantitative questionnaire that 50.6% of parents were in favor of women working in careers, with only 12.6% comfortable with them working in male-dominated environments. Surprisingly, only 25.1% of parents encouraged their daughters to choose the profession they wanted. Intizar and Arif (2025) found that students whose mothers experienced higher stress levels, particularly severe or extra severe, were more likely to perform poorly academically, thus indicating the negative correlation between parental stress and the level of academic performance of female students. Mujtaba and Lashari (2023), in a survey of female engineering students, found a direct correlation between social support and the students' performance in the learning environment.

Internationally, girls face similar barriers, with gender roles discouraging the pursuit of STEM careers from a young age, influenced by perceptions of occupational value (Low et al., 2005; Hartung et al., 2005; Eccles, 2006). According to STEM Women, globally, only 31% of female students took core STEM subjects in the year 2022 to 2023, with only 23% enrolling in computer science courses. Yang (2019), in a global research into female education in STEM, commented on the methodical approach taken by Pakistani schools. Lessons in Pakistan are typically taught using lecture-based instruction, and thus, he showed through a series of experiments how experimental learning helped boost girls' confidence and activated interactive learning. However, the situation is considerably worse in Pakistan, with women holding only 4.9% of engineering supervisory posts (Safaraz 2023, Scientia). Overall, efforts to promote girls' education in Pakistan face systemic and regional challenges, underscoring the need for broader, longitudinal, and culturally sensitive approaches. Nazli and Noman (2023) outlined that socio-cultural factors like early marriage and pregnancy, and gender norms were key to limiting female access to STEM education. An important factor of this research was that it examined these two factors in the 4 major provinces and found high rates of rigid stereotypical beliefs in Punjab and Sindh.

The gender disparity in Pakistan has been highlighted by key organizations internationally. According to the National Report on the Status of Women in Pakistan (2023), Pakistan ranks 145th on the Gender Gap Report 2022 and is above only Afghanistan. The World Bank (2024) stated that while all children are impacted by poor-quality schooling, Pakistani girls, in comparison to boys, are more greatly affected. Girls are less likely to be enrolled in school, less likely to stay in school, and less likely to achieve learning outcomes even if they attend school. The intersectionality of poverty and gender can leave most Pakistani girls without receiving a basic education. A study into female STEM education in Khairpur (Shaikh, Sahito, and Dehraj, 2019) found discouraging statistics on the topic in the region, although 69% of the female respondents believed that females did have an aptitude for STEM subjects 44% of them had a problem with attending classes with males. This speaks to the low confidence among the female students. Parental pressures also played a key role, with only 4% in agreement with their daughters pursuing STEM education. Another research study (Ihsan Ullah, Nawab, and Owais, 2024) found that low self-esteem and self-doubt were important factors determining female education in STEM. The participants stated that STEM departments were more suited for men than women and that females should to jobs in medicine and teaching. Some women seemed to associate the gender gap with biological abilities, declaring that “males think about technical things. I think this phenomenon is from God”. Kinza (2022) showed that although STEM fields are now more accessible to girls, the difference becomes more pronounced as students reach

more senior levels and leadership-oriented STEM positions. Khokhar (2018) researched the perspectives of females in academic positions in Pakistan and also commented on how, although the number of girls in STEM fields is showing a rise, females are generally absent from higher-up and decision-making positions.

While gender disparities in STEM exist globally, the intersection of patriarchy, security concerns, and marriageability pressures makes the Pakistani case particularly complex.

4. Methodology

4.1. Overview, operationalisation and pilot study.

To investigate familial support for girls in STEM in Lahore, I employed a mixed-methods approach, combining both positivist and interpretivist paradigms. Specifically:

1. Quantitative method: An online questionnaire was used to collect numerical data, allowing for generalizability and statistical analysis. The questionnaire served to highlight quantifiable steps taken by parents to help their daughters with their education.
2. Qualitative method: Unstructured interviews, which provided in-depth contextual insights into participants' experiences and perspectives.

Before conducting the main research, I conducted a pilot study to assess the feasibility, validity, and reliability of my research design. Identifying potential errors, I made changes to the survey as seemed fit to ensure correct results.

Prior to data collection, the concept of familial support was operationalized through clear indicators to ensure consistency in measurement. Common factors that were looked for included the amount of attention, economic support to provide further tuition, motivational support to pursue a desired career, taking steps to support education, hindrance in pursuing STEM careers, and parents' level of support to help the child to do further.

4.2. Quantitative Data

The target population included female school students from different locations in Lahore, Pakistan. A sample of 100 female students in O or A level was selected to fill the survey from various schools. Details of the sample are represented in the chart below. The sample was accessed through individuals like Head Girls and STEM Presidents of the school. No strict sampling frame was followed, and Presidents were made to send the questionnaire in their

respective group chats online for students to fill out the form until the required number of applicants was received.

The sample was stratified by grade level; 20 students from each grade (9 to A2) filled the sample from five different schools in Lahore. However, in some cases, schools that did not have a respective A-level or O-level programme were only asked to ensure students who fell into the respective grade filled the survey.

To address the issue of a low response rate, I sent frequent reminders to the individuals who accessed the sample, and also provided my email address and phone number so that respondents could contact me with questions or concerns. Respondents were asked for consent to include the data gathered in the research by ensuring that they first ticked the box to give their permission.

4.2.1. Sample Composition:

4.3. Qualitative Data

To gather rich, contextual insight into the perspective of the students, I also conducted unstructured interviews. This method is ideal for in-depth exploration, and the conversational style encourages detailed responses.

Respondents were put at ease to ensure a relaxed, comfortable environment.

4.3.1. Sample Composition:

10 female students were questioned for interviews, and no strict sample was followed. The participants of the online questionnaire were asked to volunteer for the interviews until the sample of 10 students was reached.

A small sample size was kept to focus more on the respondents' perspectives and provide deeper discussion. The aim was not to generalise patterns. This was done with the questionnaire.

All information was kept confidential, and participants were asked for their consent before the interviews were conducted.

Both samples had students from similar socio-economic status and mostly had access to a higher education and could afford tuition and extra help. They constituted the so called 'middle class' (Durr-e-Nayyab 2011).

The triangulation method enhanced the overall validity and reliability of my research, as well as providing depth and breadth.

5. Results

5.1. Quantitative Data

The survey distributed among students was composed of a series of questions that have been detailed below as tables with each heading featuring the question asked.

5.1.1. STEM Major to be pursued

Medicine or Biology	Chemistry	Math	Computer Science or IT	Engineering
37%	0%	8%	36%	13%

*Note: Some participants also gave responses such as "Astrology and cosmology" or preferred all options except Medicine. The number of such participants only mounted to one or two of such cases.

5.1.2. Residential Area

Urban	Rural	Semi
87%	0%	13%

5.1.3. Who makes your educational decisions?

Father	Mother	Both equally	I myself	Me and my parents
3%	8%	27%	31%	26%

*Note: Two participants mentioned their siblings as being the main makers of decisions.

5.1.4. Do your parents work?

Both	Father	Mother	Neither
29%	65%	5%	0%

5.1.5. Do your parents encourage you to pursue your academic goals?

Strongly Agree	Agree	Sometimes	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
54%	28%	14%	4%	0%

5.1.6. Are your parents supportive of your interests in STEM fields?

Yes	No	It depends
81%	3%	17%

5.1.7. Have your parents discouraged you from choosing a certain STEM subject?

Yes	No
21%	79%

5.1.8. Do your family's financial resources affect your ability to pursue STEM education?

Yes	No	Not sure
18%	54%	28%

5.1.9. Have you ever been told STEM fields are "not suitable for girls?"

Yes	No
15%	85%

5.1.10. Do your parents prioritize education for your brothers over you?

Yes	No	Not applicable
10%	63%	26%

5.1.11. Do you believe your academic performance would improve with more support from your family?

Yes	No
53%	47%

5.1.12. Have your parents spent money on extra resources like tuition or buying notes to help you with your STEM education

Yes	No
88%	12%

5.1.13. Do your parents encourage you to pursue a career?

Yes	No
90%	10%

5.1.14. Do your parents encourage you to become independent? Do they help you make decisions yourself?

Yes	No
77%	23%

5.1.15. Who is more supportive comparatively to your STEM education?

Father	Mother	Neither	Both
24%	17%	4%	47%

5.1.16. Do your parents actively engage with your teachers at school activities like PTCs? (Parent-Teacher Conference)

Yes	No	It depends
42%	12%	45%

5.1.17. Do you believe medicinal careers are the "best" for girls?

Yes	No
15%	85%

5.1.18. Do your parents believe in the "Doctor for a girl, Engineering for a boy" stereotype?

Yes	No
13%	87%

5.1.19. Did your mother pursue a STEM career? (If applicable)

Yes	No	Not applicable
27%	67%	5%

5.1.20. *Would you feel comfortable working in a male dominated environment?*

Yes	No
59%	41%

5.1.21. *Do you take inspiration from successful STEM oriented females who have made their mark? (eg Arfa Karim)*

Yes	No	Never thought about it
69%	3%	28%

5.2. Qualitative Data

Results of informal discussions with respondents have been organised into thematic sections as detailed below. Respondents were engaged in informal discussions and were allowed to express their views outside the questions asked. In addition, follow-up questions were repeatedly asked to provide further detail into aspects explored and have all been detailed in the ‘Other Notes (5.2.13)’ section. Before initiating discussion, respondents were asked about their age and the future career they wanted to pursue. The sample, consisting of 10 girls between the ages of 14 to 18, was diverse with varying interests from Computer Science to Environmental Engineering.

5.2.1. *Academic journey and Reasons for choosing current field.*

Many participants shared how their academic interests evolved due to societal and practical factors. One reflected, “Forever, I wanted to be a doctor, and for that, I had to take sciences in school. But due to the shift in the world, Computer Science is a demanding field, so I shifted my interests.” For others, personal passion remained constant, like a participant who said, “I want to pursue medicine, and I’m doing courses online to help me. The recent pandemics inspired my interest in diseases and vaccines.” Parental support also played a key role, as one shared, “I’ve always been interested in IT, and my parents support what I do.” Yet, not all had the freedom to choose; “All of South Asia believes women should just take Biology. I wasn’t given a choice in my subjects.” Another noted how school limitations affected her path: “My school

didn't offer that many subjects. I was very adamant about pursuing engineering."

5.2.2. Family's reaction to STEM pursuit

Family reactions ranged from supportive to indifferent, with underlying cultural biases. Some found encouragement, like the participant who said, "My parents have never been negative towards what I do. They want me to have a stable career." Family backgrounds in STEM were influential too: "My father has a CS degree, and I got my initial interest from him." However, cultural expectations persisted. One participant shared, "It's something they wouldn't envision their daughter doing, but they say go for it." Parental opinions often diverged: "My mother wanted me to be in Medicine, but my father was more encouraging to take CS." In some cases, science was seen as obligatory: "Not taking science would have been on my weak personality. I'm just saving myself from my parents' titles."

5.2.3. Challenges faced at home

While some participants reported no significant challenges, others described subtle pressures and cultural taunts. One shared, "My parents constantly remind me that I need to pursue a good career with a high salary." For others, gender stereotypes in STEM posed hurdles: "CS is very male-dominated, so they didn't like it. Cultural reasons also played a role." Family support varied, as some faced indifference: "It is true my family is not accepting. They haven't done anything." Minor discouragements appeared through casual remarks, such as, "My mother jokingly taunts me. She says cooking will run a house." In contrast, others were reassured by trust and pride from their families: "My parents trust me a lot. They were proud of me." Yet the fear of failure remained, with one participant stating, "When you fail, it's hideous. You are taunted and excluded."

5.2.4. Influence of traditional factors like marriage and household duties on current studies

Participants highlighted varying degrees of traditional expectations influencing their studies. Some faced subtle reminders, as one shared, "My parents want me to balance studies and household chores. They sometimes say I should walk into the kitchen and learn, but they never really forced me." For others, household duties were deprioritized: "If I'm studying or busy, my parents go out of their way to make sure nothing gets in my way." However, cultural ideals persisted in some households: "Taking Medicine, families make it feel like it's a gold standard. You'll get a good reputation, good marriage ties." Despite this, some

participants expressed strong personal boundaries, “I don’t like to do any cooking or household stuff. I want to study and go abroad.”

5.2.5. Thoughts on subject choices

Subject selection was heavily influenced by family perceptions of prestige and financial security. One participant reflected, “I was discouraged from taking Arts subjects, so I took Sciences. But I'm happy with what I take right now.” Others were steered by economic reasoning, “Computer Science has more money than the humanities.” The disregard for newer or unconventional subjects was evident: “I was discouraged from taking global perspectives because it has no money and no value.” However, a few had freedom in choice, as shared, “My parents just say do what you want.”

5.2.6. Family support that would help girls more

Participants stressed the need for emotional support and advocacy from families. One remarked, “It starts from emotional support. If you have the money but not the support, it’s useless.” Others emphasized practical support, “Maybe a personal tutor. Our school does not have a robotics tutor.” Financial prioritization of sons was also mentioned: “Parents only focus on their son’s education.” For rural areas, mindset change was crucial: “Mindset in rural areas needs to change.” The importance of allowing room for failure was highlighted, “Parents need to realize there needs to be room for failure.”

5.2.7. Aspects on which my career will focus.

For most participants, career ambitions stemmed from personal passion and the desire to contribute positively to society. One expressed, “My career will focus on my passion.” Another noted, “I want to be financially independent, but I also want to give back to my parents and community.” Social impact was a common goal: “I want to be a teacher and impact society.” Others aspired to uplift women: “I want to give back to women as well.”

5.2.8. Solution to the gender disparity

Participants believed that inspiring role models and breaking cultural barriers are key to addressing gender disparity. One said, “Girls outdo themselves, but if a greater percentage of them do, it will act as a source of inspiration for others.” The lack of education access in rural areas was a significant concern: “There are so many women out there, especially in rural areas with no access to education.” Educated mothers were seen as pivotal: “Mothers who are educated know how to take a stand for their daughters.” Financial support mechanisms like scholarships were also suggested: “Scholarships, fair scholarships.”

5.2.9. What defines “success” for a girl

Success was defined variably by participants, often influenced by family expectations. For some, it meant traditional milestones: “For my family, it’s that you get a good-paying job and by 27, you are married.” Academic excellence was also emphasized: “Get A stars and a good SAT score. Get into a good university like LUMS.” Independence and societal contribution were personal measures of success: “Success would be gaining independence and giving back to your parents.” A participant summed up, “Women who work are more reality-grounded than those who stay at home.”

5.2.10. Thoughts on empowering campaigns

Opinions on feminist campaigns like Aurat March were mixed. Some participants expressed strong support: “Yeah, women should fight for their rights in any way they can.” Others felt the message gets lost in extreme expression: “The way they express their slogans suppresses the real message and the real woman in pain.” A few voiced skepticism, “It’s not necessarily a good thing. My father believes rather than going out, we should accept peacefully at home.” Yet, there was acknowledgment of the need for awareness: “Women’s rights in Pakistan are just a paper practice; there needs to be more solid steps.”

5.2.11. Thoughts on cultural expectations

Cultural expectations regarding marriage, appearance, and gender roles were prevalent. One participant shared, “In Pakistan, they say you should be married by 25, be white and fair, skinny, and I don’t think this is going to end.” The imposition of hijab and lack of choice was also criticized: “Islamic scholars don’t explain why we have to wear a hijab; they forcefully push it on you.” Participants noted how societal norms pigeonhole women: “Pakistan thinks: Do labour, get married, get a degree, and don’t talk about it. Be an educated housewife.” The root of these issues was seen as a deep-seated mindset: “Male toxicity is promoted a lot, and this mindset encourages thoughts like women should be less dominant.”

5.2.12. Had family support not existed

While some participants claimed they would still fight for their rights, many acknowledged the pivotal role of family support. One said, “Even if my family didn’t support me, I would still try to do what I want.” Another reflected, “I am where I am because of my parents. They give me space; without it, I could not have done anything.” Some expressed a determination to rebel if needed, “Yeah, I would show them previous women in STEM and rebel.” However, the emotional impact of parental expectations was also noted: “My family has a lot

of expectations. Even if something is better than the rest of the class, they would not think that, and I might be a disappointment.”

5.2.13. Other Notes

Participants shared several nuanced reflections that revealed the underlying complexities of navigating STEM aspirations in a conservative society. For many, familial expectations hovered in the background, often subtle yet persistent. One participant remarked, “My parents would love for me to be a doctor, but they would never force me to become one.” Yet, this lack of overt forcefulness did not necessarily translate into freedom, as another participant candidly expressed, “I’m kind of guilt-tripped into taking a career. Like they don’t force me, but they do at the same time.” Despite these familial pressures, some participants had learned to distance themselves from external societal noise: “I don’t let the thoughts of my extended family get to me.”

The gender dynamics within STEM fields were a recurring point of frustration. A participant shared, “STEM is male-dominated in Pakistan, and it’s annoying. In a competition, if I have another female in the room, I feel more comfortable. They look down on you and make you doubt yourself. I prefer venting about this to my friends.” The disparity between urban opportunities and rural deprivation was starkly highlighted: “it’s crazy how hard life is for women in villages. Women are not even offered the basic education.” Favoritism in educational institutions also discouraged many: “We live in a society where there’s plenty of favoritism.” However, the value of education remained clear, with one participant stating, “Women should have careers for knowledge.”

The subject of co-education sparked varied sentiments. One participant observed, “Co-education is such a big issue in our society. People aren’t willing to accept it.” The perception of women in STEM as anomalies further alienated female students: “Women in STEM are made to feel that they are an exception; it’s not normal.” Academic choices were often dictated by economic viability rather than passion, with one participant lamenting, “There is a truth that humanities is getting unpopular and doesn’t have money for the job. It’s based on perception.” The emotional toll of academic pressure also surfaced: “My parents have started taking stress because I take it.”

Recognizing the rigid societal structures, some participants advocated for gradual change: “In a society like Pakistan, change should start slow.” The stigma attached to even traditional paths like early marriage was also highlighted: “Even if someone wants to take a traditional path and get married early, it also has such a social stigma attached to it.” Institutional limitations such as unavailability of desired subject combinations posed further challenges:

“My school didn’t offer the subject combo I wanted.” Safe academic spaces were important to some: “I feel more comfortable in an all-girls school.”

Participants were also aware of the delicate balance between parental influence and personal agency. As one put it, “Your parents' choices do matter, but at the end of the day, it’s your choices.” The feeling of invisibility within educational institutions was echoed in statements like, “Average people are not in any books of the teachers, good or bad. They might be good to me, but behind me, I’m just a dumb student.” Finally, a deeply personal reflection captured the weight of societal judgment on mothers, “When your roots are before you and nobody stands before you except your mom. You can’t tolerate anything happening to a mother who's already under influence. Society thinks that whatever a child is, it’s due to her mother.”

6. Discussion

The findings from this research highlight several critical dynamics affecting female students’ pursuit of STEM education in Pakistan. While the existing literature suggests strong patriarchal influences and cultural constraints limiting women’s educational choices, the results of this study demonstrate that these factors are not as universally restrictive as often portrayed. Instead, they reveal a more nuanced picture of familial support, societal expectations, and the personal resilience of young women navigating their educational journeys. However, it is important to note that interviews and the survey were conducted among schools with students who had the financial means to pursue further education and constituted what Durr-e-Nayyab (2011) calls the “middle class”. The literature review observed a lack of potential research among this growing group in Pakistan and was focused mostly on the villages of Pakistan. Thus, the results highlight a significant change of attitude among this class and the rise of more aware progressive middle-class parents who do not apply unfair prejudices to their daughters.

6.1. Quantitative Data

The findings of the survey provide contradicting insights into the role of familial support in shaping the academic pathways of female students pursuing STEM education. While the literature emphasizes patriarchal norms and gendered expectations limiting female participation in STEM fields, the responses gathered reflect a more complex reality where traditional stereotypes coexist with evolving family dynamics.

6.1.2. Decision-Making and Autonomy

A significant portion of the respondents (especially from senior grades like A1 and A2) indicated that they themselves or they and their parents collectively make educational decisions. This suggests a gradual shift towards increased autonomy for female students, contrasting with prevailing narratives of male-dominated decision-making in the household. Fathers still play a pivotal role in decision-making across all grade levels, indicating that while autonomy is increasing, it often operates within the boundaries set by paternal approval. However, what is important to note was that a high percentage of participants indicated that their parents supported their views.

6.1.3. Parental Encouragement and Support

Most participants reported that their parents encourage them to pursue academic goals and STEM interests, with strong agreement particularly evident in higher grade levels. The perception of STEM fields being "unsuitable for girls" was overwhelmingly refuted by the respondents. Similarly, very few girls reported that their parents prioritize education for their brothers over them, which directly contradicts common assumptions in existing literature that male education is often prioritized in Pakistani families.

6.1.4. Financial Constraints and Resource Allocation

While financial resources were not frequently cited as a limiting factor for pursuing STEM education, some students acknowledged that their families have invested in extra academic resources such as tuition and study materials. This indicates that for many families, investing in daughters' STEM education is a priority. It also points to a level of privilege within the surveyed group, as many respondents are from urban areas where access to resources is relatively better.

6.1.5. Parental Stereotypes and Career Expectations

Interestingly, responses reflect a decline in rigid gendered stereotypes like "Doctor for a girl, Engineer for a boy." Most students reported that their parents do not subscribe to this belief, although medicine remains a popular choice among female students, likely influenced by societal perceptions of it being a "safe" and "respectable" career for women. Conversely, there is a notable rise in interest in Computer Science and IT, especially among students who make independent decisions, suggesting an emerging trend of girls exploring non-traditional STEM fields beyond medicine.

6.1.6. Independence, Engagement, and Role Models

A recurring theme is the encouragement of independence among the students, with many indicating that their parents support them in becoming decision-makers regarding their education. However, active parental engagement with teachers (such as during Parent-Teacher Conferences) remains inconsistent and often dependent on grade level and parental availability. Additionally, while several students take inspiration from successful STEM-oriented female role models like Arfa Karim, many mentioned they had "never thought about it," indicating a gap in exposure to female STEM figures within family or school environments.

6.1.7. Comfort in Male-Dominated Spaces

The majority of respondents expressed confidence in working within male-dominated environments, showcasing a positive shift in perceptions regarding gendered professional spaces. This confidence is further bolstered by familial support, which, while varying in degree, exists for most participants.

6.1.8. Contradictions to Existing Literature

The data challenges the overly generalized portrayal of Pakistani families as uniformly restrictive towards girls in STEM. While patriarchal norms undoubtedly exist, there is substantial evidence of familial encouragement, shared decision-making, and a growing acceptance of diverse STEM careers for girls. The findings underscore the importance of considering socio-economic background, urban vs. semi-urban settings, and generational shifts when assessing familial influence.

6.2. Qualitative Data

6.2.1. Familial Influence and Support

The data from the interviews challenge the general assumption that all families in Pakistan impose rigid, patriarchal norms. While some respondents described families adhering to traditional gender roles, there was a notable variation in how different families supported or constrained their daughters' educational choices. Not all parents were overtly discouraging of non-traditional career paths for women. Many participants reported that their parents actively supported their aspirations in STEM fields, particularly fields of Computer Science, even when those ambitions deviated from societal norms. A common observation was that it was the father who encouraged their daughters to pursue STEM fields, while mothers felt that the field of Medicine, often commonly associated with girls, was better for their daughters. This suggests a shift in

family attitudes, particularly among more educated or urban households, where there appears to be greater openness to supporting girls in pursuing careers that were once considered unconventional for women.

6.2.2. Emotional vs. Financial Support

The interviews highlight the significant role of emotional support in shaping the respondents' educational outcomes. While financial support—such as access to private tutoring or the provision of necessary materials—was certainly important, emotional support emerged as a more critical factor in enabling female students to thrive in STEM disciplines. This contrasts with the emphasis in some studies that financial backing is the most significant determinant of success in STEM. Participants who felt emotionally supported by their families—whether through encouragement, trust, or acceptance of failure—were more likely to persist in challenging fields like Computer Science and Engineering. This highlights the importance of fostering a supportive home environment that nurtures confidence and resilience, beyond material resources. In addition, most respondents voiced their views that the solution to gender disparity was the need for more role models and motivational support.

6.2.3. Parental Expectations and Career Choices

In line with the literature, some respondents did experience pressure to conform to traditional career paths, such as Medicine, which is often seen as more suitable for women due to societal expectations. However, the study revealed that not all participants conformed to these pressures. Many respondents felt empowered to make their own career choices despite family expectations. This is contrary to some of the more deterministic portrayals in the literature, where family pressure is often seen as a major barrier to girls' participation in STEM. The flexibility that some families allowed their daughters—particularly in more urban and progressive households—suggests that the rigidity of parental influence is not as widespread as previously thought.

6.2.4. Societal Constraints: Marriage, Gender Roles, and Social Expectations

While societal pressures related to marriage and domestic roles were present in many respondents' narratives, the extent to which these pressures shaped their educational pursuits was less pronounced. Many of the respondents did acknowledge societal expectations regarding marriage and household duties, but their commitment to education and professional ambitions often outweighed these concerns. The research points to an evolving mindset among youth, where women are increasingly willing to learn to balance both work and family life. The findings suggest that while cultural expectations continue to exert some

influence, young women are becoming more self-determined and less likely to be confined by traditional ideas of success and gender roles.

6.2.5. Shifting Attitudes towards STEM

Interestingly, the study's findings align with recent shifts in attitudes toward STEM education for women. The respondents expressed a clear understanding of the barriers to entry for women in STEM fields, but also demonstrated a strong desire to break these barriers. The perception that STEM is male-dominated was acknowledged, yet many participants still showed resilience and determination to pursue these fields despite the challenges. Many girls voiced the fact that if we continue to discourage females from male-dominated fields, there will never come a time when equality will prevail.

6.2.6. The Importance of Role Models and Mentorship

A key factor identified by respondents was the importance of role models, both within their families and in the broader community. Several participants expressed a desire to see more female mentors in STEM, which would help them feel more confident in their ability to succeed. However, while mentorship was seen as valuable, the study suggests that familial support and personal drive may be more influential in determining the participants' career paths. The importance of seeing women succeed in STEM fields was acknowledged, but the study also found that many respondents were able to navigate their journeys without immediate role models, suggesting that determination and self-motivation can sometimes outweigh the need for external validation.

7. Conclusion

The research conducted revealed that while patriarchal norms and cultural expectations continue to shape the educational endeavors of female students in Pakistan, there is a significant and growing subset of families, particularly within the urban middle class, who actively support their daughters' aspirations in STEM fields. Contrary to the generalized narratives in existing literature that portray Pakistani families as uniformly restrictive, the findings illustrate a more nuanced reality where emotional encouragement, shared decision-making, and increasing autonomy are gradually dismantling traditional barriers. This suggests that the change in mindset needs to be further studied to unfold new perspectives as education and urbanisation leads many middle class families to discard traditional gender roles and adopt a more open and encouraging stance towards their daughter's education.

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